

FAMILY PERCEPTION OF CHILDREN SCHOOL ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

In recent years, we have witnessed a growing disinterest and demotivation towards school tasks by a significant portion of students in compulsory stages, who show difficulties in attributing meaning and personal value to the activities and learning they carry out in the school context (Coll, 2016). The results of some research indicate that this progressive disconnection begins in the final years of primary education and, especially, during the compulsory secondary education stage. It also suggests that this is triggered by the presence of social disadvantages, lack of interest in school content, low involvement and participation in school, the presence of early failures, and the accumulation of different problems to which the school and the immediate environment of the students do not react in a timely or effective manner. Additionally, it is added that currently, people have a large amount and variety of contexts beyond school where we can learn. This means that children and young people often find activities more aligned with their motivations and learning interests and that they derive deeper learning from contexts external to school than what they do in it, experiencing it as an obligation (Coll et al., 2020).

In response to this situation, families are concerned (González, 2015; Ito et al., 2013), especially about the serious consequences that such demotivation and disengagement can have in the medium and long term: not being able to develop the basic competencies and learning necessary to live in the 21st century, the little usefulness students attribute to what they learn in school in other contexts, the inability to achieve their personal and professional life projects, and, in the worst cases, academic failure.

This situation has motivated teaching teams and other education professionals to design and implement different methodologies and strategies to improve educational practices that take place in schools. One pedagogical approach to address this problem is personalized learning, a perspective that emphasizes student control, taking into account their voice, and recognizing their decision-making ability regarding their own learning process (Bray and McClaskey, 2015; Coll, 2018; US Department of Education, 2017).

Within the framework of a larger project, we have developed questionnaires aimed at students, teachers, and families from 14 primary and secondary educational centers of public and private ownership, and of different sizes located in different areas of Catalonia. Additionally, we have also taken into account for the selection of the centers whether they have educational projects based on customization or not. These questionnaires aimed to explore the perception of student involvement held by the different educational agents. The study presented in this communication aims to explore the perceptions of families on how they perceive their children's involvement in school activities and participation, and the factors that influence their engagement with learning and school activities. Therefore, we present the specific data from the questionnaire aimed at families.

The instrument, which consists of closed-ended questions with 4-point Likert-type responses, has three blocks of questions: the first block about sociodemographic data (8 questions), such as the number of children per family, the educational stage of their children, the family's socioeconomic level, gender, or family educational level; a second block about the perception of the degree of involvement and participation of their children in school (7); and a third block about their opinion on the implementation in the classroom of

different personalized learning strategies (15) such as, for example, working with and based on students' interests, connecting school and non-school learning experiences, or reflecting on their own learning process, among others. 914 families participated in the questionnaire.

The data analysis indicates that the majority of families point out that the level of involvement of their children in school is medium to high, regardless of the stage or characteristics of the center. Nevertheless, we have identified significant differences in some items depending on certain variables. For example, we found more positive responses regarding the importance of school for the future of their children among families from higher socioeconomic level centers and centers that personalize learning compared to those that do not. Regarding the educational stage, a significant finding is that families perceive greater support from teachers in terms of learning when their children are in primary school than in secondary or high school. As for personalized learning strategies, the results suggest a considerable level of agreement regarding the importance of personalized learning strategies to promote their children's engagement with activities and learning, regardless of the variables considered. Finally, we present a brief comparison of the perceptions of families with those of students and teachers themselves. In conclusion, possible implications of these results are discussed from the perspective of family involvement and participation in school life.

Keywords: personalized learning, school engagement, family

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